

DAMAGE AND PERMEABILITY EVOLUTION IN CFRP CROSS-PLY LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: In this study, damage and permeability in CFRP cross-ply laminates were evaluated experimentally with using cruciform specimens at room temperature. Development of matrix cracks in the CFRP laminate under biaxial loadings was acquired. Permeability of helium gas through the laminate was measured in relation to crack density and applied biaxial loads. The results of the experiments indicate that stacking sequences of CFRP laminate influence not only matrix crack development but also leakage prevention. Gas permeability through damaged CFRP composite laminates is influenced mainly by crack densities and crack opening displacements, because matrix cracks play a role as a leakage path. Permeability through the damaged laminates increases in accordance with damage development, and increasing rate of permeability in connection with the strains was approximately dominated by the external biaxial loads.

KEYWORDS: CFRP Laminate, Propellant Leak, Matrix Crack, Cruciform Specimen, Biaxial Load.

INTRODUCTION

It is significant for the developments of reusable launch vehicles (RLVs) and cryoplanes that cryogenic propellant composite tanks should be put into practical use. Various researches have been conducted for carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) composite materials to apply the cryogenic tanks, and some endeavours have been made to fabricate the CFRP composite tanks resistible to the cryogenic environment. Leakage of propellant is especially critical on the cryogenic composite tanks, even though the leakage resistibility of the composite is being improved recently. In case of the cryogenic propellant storage of liquefied hydrogen or oxygen in RLV, the defects induced in manufacturing process and operation lead the propellant leakage and may become the cause of structural fracture such as the tank failure of X-33 test vehicle through the accumulation of gases in the honeycomb core [1]. Metal or polymer liners have been considered for preventing leakage through the defects in the CFRP tanks. However these liners in the composite tanks do not only decrease the efficiency of weight reduction, but also cause problems due to difference of thermal contraction between the CFRP composite and the liner under cryogenic environment. Therefore it has been tried to examine the feasibility of CFRP propellant tanks without the liner. Several studies [2, 3] showed that severe thermal stress at cryogenic temperature of liquid hydrogen could induce matrix cracks at relatively low loads. Investigations of multiple matrix cracks in the laminate under thermal and mechanical loads were developed [4, 5], and matrix crack developments in the laminate even under thermal cycle without mechanical loads were reported [6, 7]. The continuous chain of connected matrix cracks would cause the gas leakage [8], and the leak through damaged laminates is significantly larger than the diffusion through undamaged laminates [9, 10]. The leakage for composite laminates under mechanical loads at cryogenic

temperature was experimentally investigated [11, 12], and permeability through the damaged laminate changes in connection with not only temperature variation but also applied loads. Analysis of leakage through the damaged laminate was also developed to describe the relationships between permeability and applied loadings [13-16].

For endurance and reliability of the composite tanks, it must be worthwhile to quantitatively evaluate the permeability through the composite laminates linked with damage development. In this study, permeability through the CFRP cross-ply laminates was measured experimentally in relation to matrix crack density at room temperature. Cruciform specimens were prepared to evaluate the damage and leakage properties of the cross-ply laminates under in-plane biaxial loadings. Development of matrix cracks in the CFRP laminate was detected through the use of ultrasonic C-scan. The effects of biaxial loading conditions on the damage developments were clarified compared with uniaxial tensile tests of strip laminate specimens, and permeability of helium gas through the laminate was measured in relation to crack density and applied biaxial load. The results of the experiments indicate fundamental properties of damage development and leakage of the CFRP cross-ply laminates under biaxial loadings.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Biaxial Test for Cruciform Specimen

In-plane biaxial tensile testing was applied to attain biaxial stresses on the gauge area of the cruciform laminates. The biaxial testing machine consisted of four hydraulic actuators of 250kN (tension/compression) capacity. These four actuator assemblies made two pairs, and were rigidly mounted in an octagonal box-shaped frame diagonally (Fig. 1). Each loading axis was called x- and y-axis, which coincided with 0° and 90° directions of laminate respectively. The frame was of heavy-duty welded construction, and placed horizontally. Available testing space in the machine was about 1000mm × 1000mm.

Material used in this study was carbon fiber/180°C cured epoxy HTA/#101, stacking sequences of specimens were (0/0/90/90)s and (0/90/0/90)s, and thickness of the laminates was 1mm. GFRP (glass fiber reinforced plastic) tabs were bonded on both sides of the cruciform laminate, and the geometry of the biaxial cruciform specimens is shown in Fig. 2. Four arms of the cruciform specimen were gripped by chucks connected to the four actuator equipped on the biaxial testing machine. The gauge area for leak measurement was 45mm × 45mm on the center of the biaxial specimen as shown in Fig.3.

Because of the ring reinforcement around the gauge area, stresses in the center portion of the specimen were unable to calculate directly. So it was important to comprehend the strains induced by the biaxial loads in the gauge area for calculating the stresses. Strain had been measured with strain gauges on the gauge area (Fig. 3) to the maximum of the strain range of 0.2%, in which no damage occurred on the laminate. Then, the relationships between biaxial loads and strains were acquired before leak test. In this study, the strain gauges were detached from the cruciform specimen after the strain measurements.

Uniaxial tensile tests of strip specimens were conducted for comparing the crack developments under uniaxial and biaxial stresses. The strip specimens with stacking sequence of (0/0/90/90)s and (0/90/0/90)s were 150mm long and 15mm wide with 35mm end tabs as shown in Fig. 4. For observing the damage development in both 0° and 90° layers in the uniaxial strip specimen, two types of uniaxial specimen were fabricated for each stacking sequence; one whose tensile direction was 0°, and the other whose tensile direction was 90°. Uniaxial tensile tests were carried out using INSTRON 8502 hydraulic driven testing machine

at room temperature. In the uniaxial test, elastic moduli were also acquired with using strain gauges, and used in the calculation of strain and stress in the results of the crack development under uniaxial or biaxial loadings.

Fig. 1: Biaxial testing machine

Fig. 2: Cruciform specimen

Fig. 3: Gauge area for leak test and strain gauges on central portion on cruciform specimen

Fig. 4: Strip specimen

Inspection of Matrix Cracks using Ultrasonic C-Scan

It is necessary to obtain the matrix crack density in the laminates for evaluating the effect of the damage on leakage. X-ray photography is widely adopted for observation of the damage inside composite materials. However, the penetrant for X-ray photography infiltrated in the matrix cracks might obstruct the accurate measurement of permeability. Then ultrasonic C-scan was applied for detection of matrix cracks in the laminates instead of X-ray photography.

Ultrasonic C-scan was carried out to observe the growth of matrix cracks in the CFRP laminate after each targeted loading. The results of the C-scan were obtained using a through transmission with glass reflector plate, and 25MHz transducer was used to emit and receive the ultrasonic energy. In this technique, the ultrasound passed through the specimen, reflected off the glass plate, and passed back through the specimen to the transducer. This ultrasonic C-scan with reflector plate was very sensitive to physical change, e.g. matrix crack, in the laminate. The results of the ultrasonic C-scan to observe the matrix cracks in the laminate were compared with those of X-ray photography for confirmation, and this ultrasonic C-scan technique turned out to be an effective method for damage detection for CFRP laminates.

Leak Measurement

The leak measurement system consisted of two stainless steel cups for gas supply and leak capture, a helium leak detector and a recorder for permeability and biaxial loads data as

shown in Fig. 5, and was capable to measure permeability through the planar laminate. Two stainless steel cups were padded on the planar laminate as shown in Fig. 6, and fixed on the center portion of the cruciform specimen with using a frame. Helium gas was fed to the laminate surface from gas container, and flow at very low rate through the gas supply cup to keep atmospheric pressure inside the cup. The detection cup entrapped leakage gas through the laminate specimen in the gauge area, and the helium leak detector connected to the detection cup measured the permeability. Contact area between the two cups and the laminate were sealed by O-rings to avoid undesirable leakage as shown in Fig. 6. Helium gas that leaked through the laminate could be captured concurrently with applying loads to the cruciform laminate, and it was possible to vary biaxial load level and their ratio quasistatically during the leak measurement.

Test sequence for the cruciform specimen was performed as follows. The cruciform specimen was applied first targeted biaxial loads with load ratio 1:1, which meant strain ratio 1:1 in the gauge area, and removed from the biaxial testing machine. Permeability through the specimen was measured in unloaded state, and matrix crack developing in the laminate was inspected using ultrasonic C-scan. Then the specimen was reloaded to the next targeted biaxial load level with load ratio 1:1. Repeating these steps, crack densities and permeability were acquired as functions of the maximum applied strains. Comparing the matrix crack developments in the cruciform and biaxial specimens, similar test sequence was performed for the uniaxial specimen as follows. The uniaxial strip specimen was applied first targeted load, removed from the uniaxial testing machine, and inspected with ultrasonic C-scan. Then the specimen was reloaded to the next targeted uniaxial load level, and these steps were repeated.

Fig. 5: Leakage measurement system for cruciform specimen under biaxial loading

Fig. 6: Schematic view of apparatus to detect leakage

RESULTS

Damage development

The crack development in the uniaxial (0/0/90/90)s strip specimen, which was applied tensile load to 0° direction, was inspected as shown in Fig. 7. Matrix cracks were initiated at about 230MPa (201MPa-235MPa) and increasing rapidly after the crack initiation. Tensile strain in Fig. 7 was calculated with using elastic constants of the laminates ($E_x=E_y=65.9\text{GPa}$, $\nu=0.047$). The crack development in the biaxial cruciform specimen was inspected as shown in Fig. 8. In the figure, permeability through the damaged laminate without mechanical load is also indicated. In Fig. 8, matrix crack in the gauge area of the cruciform specimen initiated at about 300MPa (269MPa-301MPa). The crack initiation occurred in 90° layer, and 0° layer was undamaged at the stress. Crack density in 90° layer of the specimen was higher than that of 0° layer after damage development, though the stress were almost same both in 0° and 90° directions.

The crack densities in (0/0/90/90)s laminates were enumerated from the C-scan images as shown in Fig.9. The enumeration of cracks in the cruciform specimen ($\sigma_y=\sigma_x$) was conducted inside the gauge area as shown in Fig. 3. In the figure, matrix crack development in surface 0° layer of the uniaxial (0/0/90/90)s strip specimen, which was applied tensile load to 90° direction ($\sigma_x=0$), was also included. Damage developments in the uniaxial strip specimens and the biaxial cruciform specimens were in good agreement irrespective of the difference of biaxial stress ratio. Matrix cracks in 90° layer developed at lower strain compared with that in 0° layer in the laminates under uniaxial and biaxial stresses.

The damage development in (0/90/0/90)s laminates was also measured, and the results are shown in Fig. 10. Damage onset of matrix cracks under biaxial stress was slightly lower than that under uniaxial stress. Matrix cracks in 90° layer of (0/90/0/90)s laminates as well as that of (0/0/90/90)s laminates developed at lower strain compared with those of 0° layer. Comparing Figs. 9 and 10, the matrix cracks was initiated at low strain in (0/0/90/90)s laminate due to thick layers compared with (0/90/0/90)s laminate.

Permeability

Developments of crack density and permeability in unloaded state of (0/0/90/90)s and (0/90/0/90)s cruciform specimens are shown as functions of applied maximum strains in Figs. 11 and 12, respectively. Matrix crack density in 0° and 90° degree layers (left vertical axis) and permeability converted to values under unit volume at atmospheric pressure per second (right vertical axis) were plotted in both figures. Leak did not provoke in the early stage of the crack development because leak path was not connected through both sides of the laminate due to some intact layers. Leakage through flow paths composed of matrix cracks was measured in the later stage of the crack development. Onset not only of matrix crack but also of leakage in (0/90/0/90)s laminate occurred at higher strain than those in (0/0/90/90)s laminate, and permeability through the (0/90/0/90)s laminate was lower than that through the (0/0/90/90)s laminate. The causes of low permeability of damaged (0/90/0/90)s laminate were supposed to be lower crack density and more complex leak paths in the laminate than (0/0/90/90)s laminate.

The damage states in the (0/90/0/90)s specimen at first and second leak measuring points were labelled as DAMAGE A and DAMAGE B as shown in Fig. 12. Permeability for

DAMAGE A and DAMAGE B of the (0/90/0/90)s cruciform specimen under biaxial loadings was measured in the load range within 20kN, in which new matrix cracks did not occur in the gauge area. Strains in the leak-strain curves were calculated with using the relationships between loads and biaxial strains as shown in Fig. 13. In fig. 13, the permeability of the damaged specimen increase in accordance with monotone increasing load. In the figure, permeability with biaxial strain ratio $\epsilon_y/\epsilon_x=1$ was largest compared with those under other biaxial strain ratio since the matrix cracks in both 90₄ and 0₂ layers opened largely under biaxial strain ratio $\epsilon_y/\epsilon_x=1$. It was significant that tensile strain caused by biaxial loadings made permeability increase remarkably, though strain values were less than 0.25%.

Increasing rates of permeability ($\epsilon_y/\epsilon_x=1, 0.43, -0.27$) for DAMAGE A and DAMAGE B were compared in Fig. 14. In the figure, each curve was normalized against their permeability in an unloaded state ($\epsilon_x=0$). Figure 14 reveals that the results in Fig. 13 have the same tendency respect to biaxial strain ratios, even though the results for DAMAGE A and DAMAGE B were quantitatively different. The quantitative difference of permeability between DAMAGE A and DAMAGE B in Fig. 13 was caused by the different amounts of matrix cracks, which made the leak paths. However, increasing rate of permeability in connection with the strains was dominated by crack opening displacements, which were driven by the external biaxial loads and approximately independent of crack densities.

CONCLUSIONS

The damage developments of the strip specimens of CFRP laminate under uniaxial loadings and the cruciform specimens under biaxial one were acquired experimentally. Biaxial tensile test with the cruciform specimens were conducted to measure the leakage characteristics through the laminate after the damage development under biaxial loadings. The results of the damage evaluation showed that the development of matrix cracks in the cruciform laminates under biaxial loads was almost the same with that in the strip laminates under uniaxial one. The results of the leak test revealed that increase of permeability through the laminate was closely related to evolution of matrix cracks and applied biaxial loads. Leakage itself was the function of the severity of matrix cracking in the laminate but the increasing rate of leakage was mainly controlled by the applied biaxial strain. Comparing the results of the CFRP laminate with different stacking sequences, the stacking sequence influenced not only matrix crack development but also permeability.

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load(kN)	stress(MPa)	strain(%)	C-Scan
3.0	201	0.31	
3.5	235	0.35	
4.0	268	0.41	
4.5	302	0.46	
5.0	335	0.51	
5.5	369	0.56	
6.0	402	0.61	

Fig. 7: Matrix crack development in strip specimen under uniaxial loading ($\sigma_y=0$)

Load (kN)	Fx	0.0	56.7	61.9	64.1
	Fy	0.0	58.0	60.2	64.7
Stress (MPa)	sigmax	0	301	334	342
	sigmay	0	313	320	348
Strain (%)	epsilonox	0	0.44	0.49	0.50
	epsilonoy	0	0.46	0.47	0.51
C-scan					
Permeability (m3/m2/s)	-	-	2.2E-10	2.7E-07	

Fig. 8: Matrix crack development in cruciform specimen under biaxial loading ($\sigma_y= \sigma_x$)

Fig. 9: Matrix crack development on (0/0/90/90)_s laminate

Fig. 10: Matrix crack development on (0/90/0/90)_s laminate

Fig. 11: Crack density and permeability as functions of maximum applied biaxial strains on (0/0/90/90)_s laminate

Fig. 12: Crack density and permeability as functions of maximum applied biaxial strains on (0/90/0/90)_s laminate

Fig. 13: Effect of biaxial strains on permeability under monotone increasing loads

Fig. 14: Comparison of increasing rate of permeability through the laminate with DAMAGE A and DAMAGE B